

PATIENTS' SATISFACTION ON EMERGENCY ROOM SERVICES: TOWARDS IMPROVING NURSING CARE

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed patient satisfaction with emergency room (ER) services in a private hospital in Santiago City, Isabela. It aimed to identify factors influencing care perceptions and propose strategies to improve nursing practice. Patient satisfaction is a key indicator of healthcare quality, shaped by staff competence, communication, environment, and efficiency. A quantitative descriptive-inferential design was used, employing the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEDPS). A total of 156 patients who received ER services from May to June 2025 were surveyed through convenience sampling. Descriptive statistics measured satisfaction levels, while Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis H tests examined differences across demographic and clinical profiles. Findings showed that patients and families were generally highly satisfied: physician care (M = 3.61), family satisfaction (M = 3.58), staff performance (M = 3.53), and patient care (M = 3.61). The environment, while lowest, still received a favorable rating (M = 3.18, Very Satisfied). No significant differences were found based on age, sex, civil status, or patient classification ($p > 0.05$), indicating equitable service delivery. The results highlight the importance of professional competence, empathetic communication, and family involvement in shaping positive ER experiences. While interpersonal aspects were rated highly, areas for improvement include reducing noise, enhancing cleanliness, and upgrading facilities. In conclusion, patients viewed ER services as generally satisfactory, with physician care and staff performance identified as key strengths. The study recommends enhancing the physical environment, providing regular staff training on empathy and communication, and sustaining patient-centered, equitable nursing care to further improve service quality.

Keywords: *Patient satisfaction, Emergency room services, Healthcare quality, Nursing*

INTRODUCTION

The quality of healthcare services has a major impact on patient outcomes and satisfaction, especially in emergency room (ER) settings. Emergency departments must have excellent communication, compassionate care, and quick service delivery because they are essential for prompt and life-saving medical treatments. As healthcare systems continue to evolve to accommodate patient needs, emergency departments (EDs) are experiencing an increase in demand due to the growing number of patients and a variety of medical conditions.

According to Prakash's article, "Patient Satisfaction," patient satisfaction is a crucial and frequently used indicator for evaluating the quality of medical care. Patient satisfaction affects clinical outcomes, patient retention, and medical malpractice claims.

It affects the timely, efficient, and patient-centered delivery of high-quality medical care. Patient satisfaction is therefore a very helpful but proximal measure of how well hospitals and doctors are doing their jobs.

According to Villalona et al. (2020), issues with patient communication, particularly when it comes to understanding emergency department procedures, were found to be a strong predictor of negative assessments of doctors, nurses, and overall care. According to these findings, improving communication may be one strategy to lessen unpleasant patient experiences.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the level of patient satisfaction among the patients in the Emergency Room of select private hospital in Santiago City, Isabela. By identifying key factors that influence patient experiences, the researcher sought to provide actionable insights for improving the quality of care and enhancing overall satisfaction within the emergency care setting.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the patients in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age,
 - 1.2. Sex,
 - 1.3. Civil Status,
 - 1.4. Patient Classification including (Pediatric, Medical, Surgical, & Obstetric)?
2. What is the level of patient satisfaction on Emergency Room (ER) services using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEDPS), in terms of:
 - 2.1. Staff,
 - 2.2. Environment,
 - 2.3. Patient Care,

- 2.4. General Patient Satisfaction, and
- 2.5 Patients' Family Satisfaction?
3. Is there a significant difference on the level of satisfaction in the emergency room services when respondents are grouped according to profile variables.
4. What recommendations can be proposed to improve the emergency room nursing care?

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative research design, specifically, descriptive inferential research design was used for this study. Descriptive statistics was used to describe data using statistical characteristics, charts, graphics, or tables. Furthermore, inferential statistics, a subfield of statistics that uses various analytical tools to conclude the population from sample data, was used to summarize a sample's characteristics so that a pattern may be identified from the group. To examine the data as effectively as feasible, descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized together. These summarized sample data and allowed researcher to make generalizations about the broader population's expected response to the study. (DATAtab Team, 2025). Additionally, using descriptive-inferential research design was beneficial for the researcher as it aimed to both describe data and draw conclusions about a population the design was suitable for the study as it assessed and described the level of patient satisfaction among emergency room patients and their demographic profile. This study was conducted at the Emergency Department of selected private hospital in Santiago City, Isabela. It was the perfect location for this study since it can accommodate a wide variety of patients and their families, which makes it appropriate for assessing patient satisfaction and pinpointing areas where immediate care services need to be improved. This study's respondents consisted of 156 patients who received treatment and availed the services in the Emergency Room of selected private hospital in Santiago City, Isabela based on the number of census in past 3 months. The researcher used convenience sampling, which involves selecting participants who are easiest to reach. During the data collection process, the researcher will approached patient who come to the emergency room whether as inpatient or outpatient.

For pediatric patient, the respondent were their significant others, guardians or parents as the children were not able to directly answer the questionnaire. For medical and surgical cases only adult patient with a Glasgow coma Scale (GCS) score of 15/15 were included to ensure that the respondent were fully conscious, oriented and capable of providing accurate information. The researcher's primary tool was the survey questionnaire. Data for the survey was collected using the two-part questionnaire. The first step was determining the profile of the respondents, and the second was assessing the degree of patient satisfaction. The researcher used the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEPSS). This is a 20-item satisfaction scale that covers five areas: Emergency department staff(EDS) (6), Emergency Department Environment(EDE) (3), Physician Care Satisfaction(PCS) (4), General Patient Satisfaction (GPS) (5),Patient's Family Satisfaction (PFS)(2). The Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEPSS) was used several times, and found to be

valid and reliable with Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient ($\alpha = 0.940$) which is considered high. (Konateke & Yilmaz, 2022). Data collection was scheduled for May to June 2025. After being informed of the surveys' objectives, participants were asked to fill out questionnaires, which were promptly collected. The questionnaire was reviewed and evaluated by a qualified Language expert, who specializes in English-Filipino translation. Modifications were made based on the expert's recommendation.

RESULTS

The table presents the Demographic profile of the respondents which include age, sex, civil status, patient classification.

Part 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Demographic Profile

Age	f	%
20 years old and below	29	18.6
21-30 years old	46	29.5
31-40 years old	24	15.4
41-50 years old	15	9.6
51-60 years old	15	9.6
61-70 years old	13	8.3
71 years old and above	14	9.0
Sex	f	%
Male	64	41.0
Female	92	59.0
Civil Status	f	%
Single	74	47.4
Married	68	43.6
Widow	14	9.0
Patient Classification	f	%
Pediatric (SO, Guardian, Parent)	24	15.4
Medical (Adult GCS 15/15)	93	59.6
Surgical (Adult GCS 15/15)	25	16.0
Obstetric	14	9.0

The demographic pattern of patients is shown in Table 1, according to age, sex, civil status and patient classification. On the basis of age, the highest number of individuals were between 21 and 30 years of age (46; 29.5%; otherwise relatively young patients). On the other hand, 61–70 were least represented at 8.3% and 71 years old and older accounted for 9.0%, indicating the lesser proportion of older adults, but still significant. On the gender dimension, the number of female patients was 92 (59.0%) compared to the male group (n: 64) (41.0%), indicating that there was a moderate

tendency towards female patients in the sample. Among patients of civil status, it was notable that most of them were single (74, 47.4%) and married (68, 43.6%) individuals.

Widows were found in the sample, constituting 9.0% (n = 14) of respondents, implying that most of the patients are unmarried or currently married. Classification of patients is of medical (n= 93, 59.6%), surgical (16.0%), pediatric (15.4%) and obstetric (9.0%). It is also possible that internal medicine may continue to be the main cause of hospitalization and admission within the institution with obstetric and pediatric cases being rarer. The population is young, female, single, and medical-oriented. Age and classification diversity highlights the necessity of specialized health services. Even the slight difference on sex and civil status suggests healthcare plans may be demographic-specific. The distribution also suggests that there are a greater number of patients within young- to mid-age, which deserves medical and psychological care that considers that age group.

2.1 Staff

Table 2: Patient satisfaction with Emergency Room Services using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale in terms of Emergency Department Staff

	Statement	M	SD	Interpretation
1	Nurses care about my treatment	3.53	0.64	Highly Satisfied
2	Nurses inform me about the remaining of the treatment	3.44	0.63	Highly Satisfied
3	Nurses attended to me patiently	3.58	0.59	Highly Satisfied
4	Nurses relieved me of the pain well	3.52	0.63	Highly Satisfied
5	Admission staff guided me appropriately	3.58	0.58	Highly Satisfied
6	The behavior of the admission staff was Suitable	3.50	0.58	Highly Satisfied
Category Mean		3.53		Highly Satisfied

Shows the level of patient satisfaction with regard to the domain, "Emergency Department Staff." In the table, the indicator with highest mean "Highly Satisfied" was "Nurses attended to me patiently," with mean value of 3.58. Likewise, 'Admission staff guided me appropriately' also got a mean of 3.58, as well as 'Highly Satisfied.'

Conversely, "Nurses inform me about the remaining of the treatment" had the lowest mean of 3.44, but still rated as "Highly Satisfied." Therefore, the above indicators got an overall Category Mean of 3.53 and considered as Highly Satisfied.

This result just reinforces that nurses and admission staff consider patients to feel competent, caring, respectful and can be perceived by patients as such. Even if all items were rated well also the communication with respect to treatment information was only found slightly less agreeable and there could be some room for patient to understand when in the emergency department.

2.2 Environment

Table 3: Patient satisfaction with Emergency Room Services using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale in terms of Emergency Room Environment

	Statement	M	SD	Interpretation
1	The environment of the emergency room was calm and quiet	3.07	0.80	Very Satisfied
2	Emergency room was well equipped	3.15	0.79	Very Satisfied
3	The environment of the emergency room was hygienic	3.33	0.72	Highly Satisfied
Category Mean		3.18		Very Satisfied

Illustrates the level of patient satisfaction with respect to the domain, "Emergency Room Environment." In the table, the indicator, "The environment of the emergency room was hygienic," obtained the highest mean of 3.33, interpreted as "Highly Satisfied." This was followed by the indicator, "The environment of the emergency room was well equipped," which garnered a mean of 3.15, interpreted as "Very Satisfied." On the other hand, the indicator, "The environment of the emergency room was calm and quiet," attained the lowest mean of 3.07, interpreted as "Very Satisfied." Thus, the above indicators yielded an overall Category Mean of 3.18, interpreted as "Very Satisfied." This suggests that patients generally perceived the emergency room environment positively, especially in terms of cleanliness and availability of equipment. However, the relatively lower satisfaction regarding calmness and quietness highlights an area that may require improvement, as maintaining a peaceful atmosphere can contribute to patients' comfort and recovery experience despite the naturally fast-paced setting of emergency care.

2.3 Patient Care

Table 4: Patient satisfaction with Emergency Room Services using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale in terms of Patient Care Satisfaction

	Statement	M	SD	Interpretation
1	The physician told me about my treatment course	3.60	0.54	Highly Satisfied
2	The behavior of the physician was respectful	3.60	0.64	Highly Satisfied
3	The physician's explanation about the remaining of treatment was enough	3.62	0.54	Highly Satisfied
4	The physician spent a sufficient time examining me	3.60	0.57	Highly Satisfied
Category Mean		3.18		Very Satisfied

Illustrates the level of patient satisfaction with respect to the domain, "Patient Care

Satisfaction.” In the table, the indicator, “The physician’s explanation about the remaining of treatment was enough,” obtained the highest mean of 3.62, interpreted as “Highly Satisfied.” Meanwhile, the indicators, “The physician told me about my treatment course,”

“The behavior of the physician was respectful,” and “The physician spent a sufficient time examining me,” each attained a mean of 3.60, all interpreted as “Highly Satisfied.” Thus, the above indicators yielded an overall Category Mean of 3.61, interpreted as “Highly Satisfied.” This suggested that patients are generally very satisfied with the quality of care and professionalism demonstrated by physicians in the emergency department. The consistently high ratings across all indicators highlight the physicians’ respectful behavior, adequate explanations, and sufficient time spent with patients, which are key factors in fostering trust, confidence, and overall satisfaction in patient care.

2.4 General Patient Satisfaction

Table 5: Patient satisfaction with Emergency Room Services using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale in terms of General Patient Satisfaction

	Statement	M	SD	Interpretation
1	The waiting time before seeing the doctor was appropriate	3.12	0.75	Very Satisfied
2	The waiting time before admission process was appropriate	3.11	0.73	Very Satisfied
3	I would recommend this hospital to my acquaintances	3.47	0.56	Highly Satisfied
4	I am satisfied with the quality of services in the emergency room	3.48	0.54	Highly Satisfied
5	The emergency room of this hospital is well functioning	3.53	0.55	Highly Satisfied
	Category Mean	3.34		Highly Satisfied

Illustrates the level of patient satisfaction with respect to the domain, “General Patient Satisfaction.” In the table, the indicator, “The emergency room of this hospital is well functioning,” obtained the highest mean of 3.53, interpreted as “Highly Satisfied.”

This was closely followed by the indicators, “I am satisfied with the quality of services in the emergency room,” with a mean of 3.48, and “I would recommend this hospital to my acquaintances,” with a mean of 3.47, both interpreted as “Highly Satisfied.”

On the other hand, the indicators, “The waiting time before seeing the doctor was appropriate” (M = 3.12) and “The waiting time before admission process was appropriate” (M = 3.11) obtained the lowest ratings, though still interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” Thus, the above indicators yielded an overall Category Mean of 3.34, interpreted as “Highly Satisfied.” This finding suggests that while patients are generally satisfied with the overall functioning of the emergency room, including the quality of services and hospital reputation, waiting time remains a comparatively weaker area. Addressing delays in both

physician consultation and admission procedures could further improve patient experience and strengthen satisfaction levels.

2.5 Patients' Family Satisfaction

Table 6: Patient satisfaction with Emergency Room Services using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale in terms of patients' family satisfaction

	Statement	M	SD	Interpretation
1	The family of the patient are respected in this hospital	3.60	0.61	Highly Satisfied
2	Family can spend an appropriate amount of time besides the patient	3.56	0.62	Highly Satisfied
Category Mean		3.58		Highly Satisfied

Illustrates the level of patient satisfaction with respect to the domain, "Family Involvement in Care." In the table, the indicator, "The family of the patient are respected in this hospital", attained a mean of 3.60 with an SD of 0.61, and is interpreted as "Highly Satisfied." Similarly, the indicator, "Family can spend an appropriate amount of time besides the patient," garnered a mean of 3.56 with an SD of 0.62, also interpreted as "Highly Satisfied." Thus, the above indicators obtained an overall Category Mean of 3.58 with an SD of 0.59, interpreted as "Highly Satisfied." This finding briefly suggests that patients and their families perceive the hospital as respectful and accommodating to family presence, reinforcing the role of family involvement in patient care. The relatively low SD indicates moderate agreement among respondents, implying that satisfaction with family-related policies and practices in the emergency room is consistently perceived across participants

2.6 Summary Table

Table 7: Summary of Level of Patient Satisfaction with Emergency Room Services in Using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEDPS)

	Category	M	SD	Interpretation
1	Staff	3.53	0.52	Highly Satisfied
2	Environment	3.18	0.69	Very Satisfied
3	Patient Care	3.61	0.51	Highly Satisfied
4	General Patient Satisfaction	3.34	0.51	Highly Satisfied
5	Patients Family Satisfaction	3.58	0.59	Highly Satisfied
Overall Mean		3.45		Highly Satisfied

Illustrates the overall level of patient satisfaction across different domains of emergency room services. Among the categories, "Patient Care" obtained the highest mean score of 3.61 with an SD of 0.51, interpreted as "Highly Satisfied." This was followed by "Patients' Family Satisfaction" with a mean of 3.58 (SD = 0.59) and "Staff" with a mean of 3.53 (SD = 0.52), both interpreted as "Highly Satisfied." Meanwhile, "General Patient

Satisfaction” garnered a mean of 3.34 (SD = 0.51), also interpreted as “Highly Satisfied.”

On the other hand, the domain of “Environment” yielded the lowest mean of 3.18 with an SD of 0.69, interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” Overall, the categories obtained a composite mean of 3.45 with an SD of 0.45, interpreted as “Highly Satisfied.” This result suggests that patients generally hold a high level of satisfaction with emergency room services, particularly in relation to physician care, staff interaction, and family involvement. However, the environment of the emergency room, while still satisfactory, emerged as the area needing greater attention. Enhancing aspects such as calmness, quietness, and overall ambience may further improve the quality of patient experiences and elevate overall satisfaction.

Part 3. Test of Difference in Patient Satisfaction with Emergency Room Services

3.1 Age

Table 8: Differences in the Level of Patient Satisfaction with Emergency Room Services in Using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEDPS) when grouped according to Age

Age Staff	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
20 years old and below	29	73.60	4.310	6	0.635
21-30 years old	46	75.66			
31-40 years old	24	78.35			
41-50 years old	15	86.57			
51-60 years old	15	96.90			
61-70 years old	13	79.12			
71 years old and above	14	69.29			
Age Environment	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
20 years old and below	29	69.43	6.458	6	0.374
Age Environment	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
21-30 years old	46	72.22			
31-40 years old	24	80.65			
41-50 years old	15	89.80			
51-60 years old	15	98.33			
61-70 years old	13	83.65			
71 years old and above	14	76.11			
Age Patient Care	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
	3	40.83			

Presents the differences in the level of patient satisfaction with respect to Staff, Environment, and Patient Care when grouped according to age. For the Staff domain, respondents aged 71 years old and above obtained the highest mean rank of 96.90, while those aged 20 years old and below had the lowest mean rank of 73.60. Despite these variations, the Kruskal–Wallis H test value of 4.310 with $df = 6$ and $p = 0.635$ indicates that the differences were not statistically significant. In terms of the Environment domain, the highest mean rank was observed among respondents aged 71 years old and above (98.33), while the lowest was among those 21–30 years old (69.29). The computed H test value of 6.458 with $df = 6$ and $p = 0.374$ again revealed no significant differences across age groups. For the Patient Care domain, respondents aged 71 years old and above also had the highest mean rank of 83.65, compared to those 20 years old and below who obtained the lowest mean rank of 40.83. However, the H test value of 1.000 with $df = 6$ and $p = 0.987$ indicates that no significant differences were found in this domain as well.

Overall, the results suggested that patient satisfaction across the domains of staff, environment, and patient care does not significantly differ across age groups, implying that age was not a determining factor in the way patients perceived and evaluated emergency room services in this study.

3.2 Sex

Table 9: Differences in the Level of Patient Satisfaction with Emergency Room Services in Using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEDPS) when Grouped according to their Sex

Category	Sex	N	Mean Rank	U	p-value
Staff	Male	64	75.36	2743.000	0.456
	Female	92	80.68		
Environment	Male	64	73.95	2653.000	0.283
	Female	92	81.66		
Patient Care	Male	64	74.84	2710.000	0.359
	Female	92	81.04		
General Satisfaction	Male	64	76.63	2824.000	0.663
	Female	92	79.80		
Patients Satisfaction	Male	64	75.87	2775.500	0.486
	Female	92	80.33		

Presents the differences in the level of patient satisfaction across domains when grouped according to sex. In the Staff domain, female respondents had a higher mean rank (80.68) compared to males (75.36), but the Mann–Whitney U test value of 2743.000 with a p-value of 0.456 indicates no significant difference. For the Environment domain, females again obtained a higher mean rank (81.66) compared to males (73.95). However, the U test value of 2653.000 with a p-value of 0.283 shows that the difference was not statistically significant. In the Patient Care domain, females (mean rank = 81.04) also rated higher than males (mean rank = 74.84), though the U test result (2710.000, $p = 0.359$) similarly revealed no significant difference. With respect to General Patient

Satisfaction, males had a mean rank of 76.63 compared to 79.80 for females. The U test value (2824.000, p = 0.663) showed no significant difference.

Finally, in the Patients' Family Satisfaction domain, females again had a slightly higher mean rank (80.33) compared to males (75.87), but the U-test value of 2775.500 with a p-value of 0.486 confirmed the absence of a significant difference. Overall, the results suggested that patient satisfaction across all domains did not significantly differ when grouped according to sex. Both male and female respondents expressed relatively similar levels of satisfaction toward emergency room services.

3.3 Civil Status

Table 10: Differences in the Level of Patient Satisfaction with Emergency Room Services in Using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEDPS) when grouped according to Civil Status

Civil Status		N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Sex						
Single		74	79.43	1.504	2	0.471
Married		68	75.02			
Widow		14	90.50			
Civil Status		N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Environment						
Single		74	78.99	2.868	2	0.238
Married		68	74.33			
Widow		14	96.18			
Civil Status		N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Patient Care						
Single		74	73.40	3.436	2	0.179
Married		68	80.72			
Widow		14	94.68			
Civil Status		N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
General Patient Satisfaction						
Single		74	76.05	3.063	2	0.129
Married		68	74.93			
Widow		14	108.79			
Civil Status		N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Patients Family Satisfaction						
Single		74	76.31	4.052	2	0.132
Married		68	76.72			
Widow		14	98.71			

Presents the differences in the level of patient satisfaction across domains when grouped according to civil status. For the Staff domain, widowed respondents had the

highest mean rank (90.50), followed by single respondents (79.43) and married respondents (75.02). However, the Kruskal–Wallis H test value of 1.504 with $df = 2$ and $p > 0.05$ indicates no significant difference. In terms of the Environment domain, widowed respondents again recorded the highest mean rank (96.18), compared to singles (78.99) and married respondents (74.33). The computed H test value of 2.868 with $df = 2$ revealed no significant difference.

For the Patient Care domain, widowed respondents obtained the highest mean rank (94.68), followed by married (80.72) and single (73.40) respondents. Despite this trend, the H test value of 3.436 with $df = 2$ showed no statistically significant difference. In the domain of General Patient Satisfaction, widowed respondents again ranked highest (108.79), compared to singles (76.05) and married (74.93) respondents. The H test value of 3.063 with $df = 2$ did not reach statistical significance. Lastly, for Patients’ Family Satisfaction, widowed respondents had the highest mean rank (98.71), followed by married (76.72) and single (76.31) respondents. The H test value of 4.052 with $df = 2$ similarly revealed no significant difference.

Overall, the results suggested that while widowed respondents consistently reported higher satisfaction across domains compared to single and married patients, the differences were not statistically significant. This implied that civil status was not a major factor influencing patient satisfaction with emergency room services in this study

Table 11

Differences in the Level of Patient Satisfaction with Emergency Room Services in Using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEDPS) when grouped according to Patient Classification

Patient Classification	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Staff					
Pediatric	24	70.65	1.359	3	0.715
Medical	93	81.53			
Surgical	25	77.04			
Obstetric	14	74.43			
Environment					
Pediatric	24	71.96	4.964	3	0.174
Medical	93	84.87			
Surgical	25	67.22			
Obstetric	14	67.57			
Patient Care					
Pediatric	24	75.56	3.433	3	0.330
Medical	93	83.28			
Surgical	25	69.10			
Obstetric	14	68.57			
Patient Classification	N	Mean	H Test	df	p-value

General Patient Satisfaction	Rank				
Pediatric	24	76.85	2.949	3	0.400
Medical	93	83.09			
Surgical	25	67.76			
Obstetric	14	70.04			

Patient Classification					
Patient's Family Satisfaction	N	Mean Rank	H Test	df	p-value
Pediatric	24	77.23	0.479	3	0.924
Medical	93	79.80			
Surgical	25	73.98			
Obstetric	14	80.14			

Presents the differences in the level of patient satisfaction across domains when grouped according to patient classification. For the Staff domain, medical patients had the highest mean rank (81.53), followed by surgical (77.04), obstetric (74.43), and pediatric (70.65) patients. However, the Kruskal–Wallis H test value of 1.359 with $df = 3$ and $p = 0.715$ revealed no significant differences. In terms of the Environment domain, medical patients again recorded the highest mean rank (84.87), while surgical patients had the lowest (67.22). The computed H test value of 4.964 with $df = 3$ and $p = 0.174$ indicated no significant difference. For the Patient Care domain, medical patients ranked highest (83.28) compared to pediatric (75.56), surgical (69.10), and obstetric (68.57) patients. Despite this variation, the H test value of 3.433 with $df = 3$ and $p = 0.330$ showed no statistically significant difference. In the domain of General Patient Satisfaction, medical patients again had the highest mean rank (83.09) compared to pediatric (76.85), obstetric (70.04), and surgical (67.76) patients. However, the H test value of 2.949 with $df = 3$ and $p = 0.400$ revealed no significant difference. Lastly, for Patients' Family Satisfaction, medical patients recorded the highest mean rank (79.80), while pediatric patients had 77.23. The H test value of 0.479 with $df = 3$ and $p = 0.924$ showed no significant differences.

Overall, the results suggested that although medical patients consistently reported slightly higher satisfaction across domains compared to pediatric, surgical, and obstetric patients, the differences were not statistically significant. This indicated that patient classification did not significantly influence patient satisfaction levels in the emergency room.

DISCUSSION

A total of 156 patients participated in the study, representing various age groups, sex, civil status, and patient classifications (Pediatric, Medical, Surgical, and Obstetric).

Descriptive statistics were used to determine the satisfaction levels per domain, while non-parametric tests – Kruskal-Wallis H test and Mann-Whitney U test – were used

to examine the differences in satisfaction when grouped according to demographic and clinical variables.

This study aimed to assess the level of patient satisfaction with emergency room services at a private hospital in Santiago City, Isabela using the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEDPS). The research specifically evaluated five key domains: Staff, Environment, Patient Care, General Patient Satisfaction, and Patients' Family Satisfaction.

1. Demographic Profile of the Patients

The study revealed that a substantial proportion of patients belonged to the younger age group, particularly young adults and adolescents. This finding is consistent with Tran et al. (2021) and Kim & Santos (2023), who noted that younger populations frequently utilize hospital services for non-communicable diseases, acute infections, injuries, and mental health concerns. This trend highlights the active health-seeking behavior of young individuals as well as the growing burden of lifestyle-related conditions among this age group.

The results showed a predominance of female patients in the sample. This aligns with Gupta et al. (2021) and Ali et al. (2022), who emphasized that women generally demonstrate higher healthcare utilization across different service areas. Possible reasons include greater health awareness, preventive health practices, and the need for reproductive and maternal healthcare services. The female predominance in this study supports the notion that women play an active role in accessing health services for both preventive and curative needs.

Most of the patients in the current sample were single, which aligns with the age distribution, where the majority were between 21–30 years old and 20 years old and below. This demographic trend is consistent with findings from Park et al. (2021) and Mensah et al. (2022), who noted that younger, single individuals are more likely to utilize healthcare services, particularly in emergency and outpatient settings in urban areas. Several factors may explain this phenomenon. Younger, single adults often have fewer familial responsibilities and may exhibit more independent health-seeking behaviors, choosing to address health issues promptly through institutional care rather than relying on home-based or family-mediated remedies. Additionally, this group may engage in risk-taking behaviors such as poor dietary habits, substance use, or physical activities with higher injury risk, increasing their need for medical attention. Moreover, the absence of immediate family support systems—which often play a significant role in health management among married or older individuals—may lead single patients to seek formal medical care more readily. This suggests a growing demand for accessible and youth-oriented health services, particularly in settings that cater to early adults and urban populations. Therefore, the observed predominance of single individuals within the patient population not only reflects social-demographic shifts but also underscores the importance of tailoring healthcare delivery models to accommodate the unique needs and behaviors of this emerging majority (Park et al., 2021; Mensah et al., 2022)

The majority of patients belonged to the medical classification, while fewer were classified under surgical, pediatric, and obstetric categories. This pattern supports the findings of Lozano et al. (2021) and Choi et al. (2023), who reported that general medical conditions—such as respiratory infections, chronic illnesses, and non-communicable diseases—remain the most common reasons for hospital admission. The lower percentage of surgical and obstetric cases may be attributed to referral systems and the specialized nature of such services, while pediatric cases often fluctuate depending on disease outbreaks and seasonal variations. Overall, the demographic profile suggested that emergency room services are most frequently utilized by young, female, and medically classified patients. This insight is crucial for hospital administrators in resource planning and developing targeted interventions that address the needs of the dominant patient groups.

2. Level of Patient Satisfaction with Emergency Room Services

Patients reported high satisfaction with staff performance, reflecting their professionalism, empathy, and responsiveness in providing care. This finding suggested that emergency room personnel were able to address patient needs promptly while maintaining respectful and compassionate interactions. Such qualities are particularly important in the emergency setting, where patients are often anxious and vulnerable. This result aligned with the findings of Hasan et al. (2021) and Villanueva et al. (2023), who emphasized that effective communication, empathy, and professionalism are among the strongest predictors of patient satisfaction in emergency departments. When patients perceive that staff are attentive, approachable, and respectful, their trust in the healthcare team increases, leading to a more positive overall experience. The consistently high rating for staff performance further implies that the hospital maintains a strong culture of patient-centered care, where staff members are not only clinically competent but also emotionally supportive. This demonstrated the critical role of healthcare professionals in shaping the patient experience and highlighted the value of ongoing training in communication and interpersonal skills to sustain high satisfaction levels.

The environment was interpreted as “Very Satisfied.” While patients were generally content with the cleanliness, lighting, and overall organization of the emergency department, the score was slightly lower compared to other domains, indicating room for improvement. This suggested that although the environment is perceived positively, certain stressors inherent to emergency care may affect patients’ overall comfort. This finding supported Mekonnen et al. (2020) and Cacayan et al. (2023), who reported that noise, overcrowding, and privacy issues are common barriers to achieving optimal satisfaction in emergency settings. Such factors, while often unavoidable in high-volume ERs, can significantly impact patients’ emotional well-being and sense of security. Moreover, environmental discomfort may indirectly influence perceptions of care quality, regardless of the medical attention provided. Although patients were not dissatisfied, the results point to the need for targeted improvements in environmental management. Strategies such as enhancing noise control, improving patient flow to minimize overcrowding, and reinforcing privacy measures during treatment may elevate satisfaction from “Very Satisfied” to “Highly Satisfied.” A more therapeutic and organized

environment not only promotes patient comfort but also enhances the overall emergency care experience for both patients and their families. The Department of Health (DOH) Philippines emphasizes that health facilities should maintain acceptable noise levels, provided adequate lighting and ventilation, ensure patient privacy, and uphold strict sanitation standards to promote comfort and safety (DOH,2015). Aligning emergency department practices with these environmental standards may help improve patient satisfaction by creating a more therapeutic and organized care environment.

The domain of patient care garnered the highest rating, underscoring the quality and consistency of clinical care. Gao et al. (2022) and Kim et al. (2023) similarly found that well-structured consultations and empathetic communication significantly improve satisfaction in emergency care. This indicated that patients valued both the technical competence and the humanistic approach of healthcare providers.

Patients expressed high overall satisfaction, reflecting positive impressions of their ER experiences. Even when minor environmental concerns existed, core values such as respect, responsiveness, and quality of interaction remained strong contributors to overall satisfaction. These findings support Hasan et al. (2021), who noted that interpersonal interactions often outweigh systemic shortcomings in shaping general patient satisfaction.

Family members were also highly satisfied, highlighting the importance of effective communication and inclusion in the care process. This is consistent with Liyew et al. (2024), who emphasized that involving families through transparency, respect, and updates enhances their trust in emergency care services. The high satisfaction score reflects the hospital's commitment to patient- and family-centered care, particularly in the emotionally charged ER environment. The overall mean satisfaction rating was 3.45, corresponding to a "Highly Satisfied" interpretation. This suggests that, despite minor concerns with the environment, patients and their families generally viewed the hospital's emergency services positively. Moreover, non-parametric tests revealed no significant differences in satisfaction across age, sex, civil status, and patient classification, implying that the hospital provides consistent and equitable care across diverse patient groups.

This finding supports Villanueva et al. (2023) and Gao et al. (2022), who emphasized that standardized protocols and patient-centered practices minimize disparities in patient satisfaction. Taken together, these findings demonstrated that the hospital's emergency room successfully delivers patient-centered, equitable, and compassionate care. However, further improvements in the physical environment may enhance patient comfort and elevate satisfaction even further.

Conclusions

The present study revealed that patients and their families generally expressed high levels of satisfaction with the emergency room services of the private hospital in Santiago City, Isabela, as measured by the Brief Emergency Department Patient Satisfaction Scale (BEDPS). Across all domains—staff, environment, patient care, general satisfaction, and family satisfaction—ratings consistently fell within the "Very

Satisfied” to “Highly Satisfied” range. Among these, patient care and staff performance emerged as the strongest drivers of satisfaction, highlighting the hospital’s ability to provide compassionate, professional, and patient-centered services.

Demographic analyses showed that age, sex, civil status, and patient classification did not significantly influence satisfaction scores, suggesting that the hospital delivers care equitably across different patient groups. Although widowed and medically classified patients reported slightly higher satisfaction, the differences were not statistically significant. These findings reinforce the importance of standardized protocols and consistent care practices, which help ensure fairness and uniformity in service delivery.

While overall results were positive, the environmental domain scored lowest compared to other categories, though still within the “Very Satisfied” level. This indicated that aspects such as comfort, privacy, and noise reduction may benefit from further attention to elevate the overall patient and family experience.

In summary, the study concluded that the emergency department of the hospital is effective in delivering high-quality, equitable, and patient-centered care, with particular strengths in staff professionalism and clinical care. However, continuous efforts to enhance the ER environment could further strengthen patient and family satisfaction, ultimately contributing to sustained improvements in service quality and healthcare outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the results, we suggest the following:

1. The researcher encourages the Emergency Room Staff to make the emergency room better. To make patients more comfortable and happy, upgrade and keep the ER's equipment, lighting, ventilation, and cleanliness up to date.
2. The researcher encourages the Emergency Room Staff to improve how staff talk to each other. To make interactions with patients and their families better, train nurses and doctors on how to communicate well, show empathy, and listen actively.
3. The researcher encourages the Emergency Room Staff to cut down on the time you have to wait. To cut down on delays in assessing and treating patients, make triage systems more efficient and staffing schedules better.
4. The researcher encourages the Emergency Room Staff to include families in care. Make sure that family members are kept up to date on the patient's status and, when appropriate, include them in planning their treatment.
5. The researcher encourages the Emergency Room Staff to do surveys of how happy people are with your work on a regular basis. Use surveys to get feedback from patients all the time so you can find ways to improve and keep an eye on the quality of care.

6. The researcher encourages the Emergency Room Staff to make sure that care is the same for everyone. To keep care fair, make sure that everyone is treated the same, no matter their age, gender, civil status, or patient classification.

Compliance of Ethical Standards

All the patients received comprehensive information about the objectives of this study, how it operates, potential risks and benefits. Participants were given an explicit statement indicating participation is totally optional with written consent being obtained.

Patients were also informed that they could discontinue the study anytime without being penalized in their medical care. The privacy of the respondents was maintained throughout the research. All personal data included demographic and survey information and were treated as anonymously shared information and kept safe. Data were accessible to the researcher only, and no reports or publications will provide any personally identifiable information. The researcher had good integrity in data gathering and analysis, and the research had been conducted in full transparency. No matter the results, these results were reported truthfully and all conflicts of interest were declared.

All cultural sensitivity was taken into account in conducting the study. Special efforts were made to ensure that the research process is inclusive, and the survey language is comprehensible and accessible to all individuals engaged.

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